

An Investigation into the Job Satisfaction among Private College Lecturers in Malaysia

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Abstract: The purpose of this study was to examine the job satisfaction of 60 private college lecturers from two Bornean states of Malaysia, by administering the Job Satisfaction Survey. A Mann-Whitney U test was used to determine if any significant gender differences, while a Kruskal-Wallis H test was used to determine if any significant age and experiential differences existed in the job satisfaction of college lecturers. Significant age differences were found in the domain of coworkers, while significant experiential differences were found in the domains of benefits and coworkers. Additionally, Wilcoxon signed-rank test using a test value of 4.0 revealed that eight out of the nine factors of job satisfaction in terms of agreement/disagreement were significant. Mean scores on all nine factors were low, indicating that lecturers experienced low job satisfaction. In light of the findings, several recommendations were made to improve the job satisfaction of private college lecturers.

Keywords: Job satisfaction, Malaysian private college lecturers.

I. INTRODUCTION

Job satisfaction has been a widely researched component of organisational behaviour since its conceptualisation (Hoppock & Spiegler, 1937). Researching this affective attribute is useful because it has serious implications on the health and psychological wellbeing of employees, which in turn, affects the performance, sustainability and reputation of an organisation. One way to retain staff in today's competitive environment is by hiring fully engaged individuals with high job satisfaction (Abraham, 2012). Research is needed to identify the factors associated with job satisfaction among college lecturers so that the management can create a sustainable environment for them to experience high job satisfaction leading to professional engagement.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Fatimah, Amiraa and Halim (2011) examined the relationships between organizational justice, organisational citizenship behaviour and job satisfaction of 169 secondary school teachers in Malaysia. Findings showed the following: (a) a significant relationship between organisational justice and job satisfaction, (b) significant relationships between procedural justice, interactional justice and distributive justice and job satisfaction, (c) organisational justice and interactional justice contributed most to job satisfaction, and (d) a significant relationship between organisational citizenship behaviour and job satisfaction.

Arokiasamy, Huam and Abdullah (2013) examined the job satisfaction of 75 academic staff from three private colleges in Malaysia in relation to compensation, motivation and promotion. Findings indicated that job satisfaction of academic staff was significantly related to pay, promotion and fringe benefits. The highest correlation was between compensation and job satisfaction, while pay was a significant predictor of job satisfaction. On the other hand, Mustapha (2013) examined the effect of financial rewards on the job satisfaction of 320 full-time academic staff at public universities in Malaysia. Findings revealed a positive significant correlation between remuneration and job satisfaction; salary tended to represent antecedent conditions of general satisfaction and have a significant impact on job satisfaction.

Mustafa et al. (2014) examined the relationship between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction of 138 technical teachers from vocational and technical colleges in Malaysia. Findings showed that technical teachers exhibited emotional intelligence and job satisfaction at a moderate level. A significant relationship between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction was found. Additionally, emotional intelligence tended to vary according to work experience. On the other hand, Abdullah and Hui (2014) who examined the relationship between communication satisfaction and job satisfaction of 226 primary school teachers in Malaysia, found that job satisfaction was significantly related to several communicational variables, including horizontal and informal communication, communication climate, personal feedback and organisational perspectives. Further, Wahab et al. (2014) examined the impact of transformational leadership practices on the job satisfaction of 240 teachers in Malaysia. Four dimensions of transformational leadership were assessed, including ideal influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation and individual consideration. Findings revealed a significant relationship between the level of transformation leadership and teachers' job satisfaction; a significant relationship between the level of transformational leadership and teachers' work commitment was also found.

Wan Ahmad and Abdurahman (2015) examined the job satisfaction of 21 psychology and social work lecturers at a university in Malaysia. Findings showed that a majority of the lecturers exhibited a moderate level of job satisfaction; only few had a high level of job satisfaction. Moreover, lecturers' job satisfaction was influenced by the nature of staff relationships as peers could bring a sense of social belonging and fulfil social and psychological needs. Since many of them had worked at the university for several years, they were satisfied with the scope of work as well as remuneration as senior lecturers.

Ghavifekr and Pillai (2016) examined the relationship between school organisational climate and the job satisfaction of 245 secondary school teachers in Malaysia. Findings revealed a significant positive relationship between school organisational climate and job satisfaction. The teachers were found to be fairly satisfied with their job, with responsibility as the biggest contributor to job satisfaction. Additionally, significant differences in job satisfaction were found in relation to years of service. On the other hand, Hanaysha (2016) examined the impact of employee engagement, employee motivation, work environment and organisational learning on the job satisfaction of 242 employees from public universities in Malaysia. Findings indicated that employee engagement, employee motivation, work environment and organisational learning had significant effects on job satisfaction. Overall, the four factors explained 75 percent of the total variance in job satisfaction.

Shen, Basri and Asimiran (2018) examined the relationship between the job stress and job satisfaction of 249 teachers from private and international schools in Malaysia. Their findings showed that teachers from international schools experienced significantly higher level of job satisfaction compared to those from private schools. Further, intrinsic motivation was significantly associated with job satisfaction. The teachers from international schools experienced significantly lower levels of job stress compared to the teachers from private schools. Work-related stressors and professional distress contributed to the significant differences in job stress between the teachers from private and international schools. The private school teachers experienced work-related stressors and professional distress most, compared to all other factors. Additionally, Nordin, Mustafa and Abdul Razzaq (2019) examined the impact of headmaster leadership on the job satisfaction of special education teachers in Malaysia by interviewing 11 coordinators. The results indicated that a majority of the teachers agreed that the leadership of the headmasters significantly influenced their job satisfaction. Further, teachers maintained that democratic leadership had greatly facilitated them to perform their duties. They also preferred headmasters who understood the needs of teachers as well as the challenges faced by students with special needs. Finally, they maintained that headmasters with special education knowledge were more effective than those without.

Ong, Siah and Tan (2020) examined the dimensions of job satisfaction among 121 Chinese independent school teachers in relation to several demographic factors. The findings showed that the two main dimensions of teacher job satisfaction were job interest and working environment. Further, years of teaching and job satisfaction were positively correlated, while income and job satisfaction were negatively correlated. Teachers who held administrative positions and had more years of teaching experience showed greater job satisfaction in terms of rewards. However, higher income was negatively correlated with working environment, salary, benefits and workload. Lastly, age was positively correlated with workload and interest in the job. Lashkariani & Motevalli (2020) examined the influence of job stress on the job satisfaction of female lecturers from a university in Malaysia. The findings revealed that three predictor variables (work group support, workload pressure, and coping skills) were significant in explaining job satisfaction, explaining 59 percent of the variance in job satisfaction. A significant relationship between job stress and job satisfaction was found; while job stress was mainly moderated by coping skills, job satisfaction was mainly moderated by promotion and remuneration.

Leow, Lee and Leow (2020) examined the relationship between job satisfaction and the wellbeing of 111 high school teachers in Malaysia by administering the Teacher Job Satisfaction Scale and Short Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Wellbeing Scale. The findings revealed a significant positive correlation between teacher job satisfaction and wellbeing; teacher satisfaction with student behaviour and parents were significant predictors of mental wellbeing. In general, teacher job satisfaction was significantly related to positive personal relationships with co-workers, students and parents. Further, Mokhtar et al. (2021) examined the teacher commitment, self-efficacy and job satisfaction of 984 trained primary schoolteachers in Malaysia. The mediating effect of self-efficacy in relation to job satisfaction and teacher commitment was tested using the motivation-hygiene theory. Findings revealed that self-efficacy significantly mediated the relationship between teacher commitment and job satisfaction; while teacher commitment and self-efficacy had a significant influence on the job satisfaction, self-efficacy tended to increase teacher commitment and job satisfaction.

Mohamed et al. (2021) examined the relationships among burnout, psychological distress and the job satisfaction of 259 academicians and 152 non-academicians in Malaysia. The findings revealed significant mean differences in the job satisfaction between the two groups, with non-academicians experiencing greater job satisfaction than academicians. Job satisfaction also tended to be negatively correlated with burnout; staff with higher burnout levels tended to exhibit lower job satisfaction. Sukmayanti and Eva (2023) who examined the influence of school climate and self-efficacy on the job satisfaction among 107 teachers found significant and positive relationships among school climate, self-efficacy and job satisfaction. Findings implied simultaneous correlations among the three variables; the better the school climate and self-efficacy, the higher the job satisfaction will be.

Niu et al. (2023) who examined the effects of both teacher- and school-level factors on teacher job satisfaction in Japan and South Korea obtained the following results: (1) gender significantly predicted teacher job satisfaction in both countries, with females having a lower level of job satisfaction than males; teaching experience was a significant predictor; teachers who had worked longer had lower job satisfaction for both countries, (2) social utility motivation to teach, self-efficacy, teacher-student relations, team innovativeness and professional development barriers were all significant predictors for teacher job satisfaction in both countries and (3) the predictor of needs for professional development had different effects on teacher job satisfaction, which was positively associated with teacher job satisfaction in South Korea but not in Japan.

Shrestha and Agrawal (2024) examined the job satisfaction among 250 teachers at private and public campuses. Their findings showed that both extrinsic and intrinsic factors tended to be significant determinants of job satisfaction among teachers teaching in the higher education sector. Lastly, Islam and Afrin (2024) examined the factors of job satisfaction of 377 faculty members at private universities. Findings showed that faculty members tended to significantly regard teaching as a good job followed by competitive payment, adequate job responsibility and opportunity to give advice. Additionally, supervisor's competence in decision making, positive staff relationships, work diversity, supervisor's technical knowledge and organizational policies were also found to be important factors of job satisfaction. One finding implied that the confidence of faculty members can be substantially improved through appropriate administrative behaviour and efficient supervision of their work.

A. Significance of the study

As seen above, several studies had been conducted in Malaysia to examine the job satisfaction of teachers and college lecturers using various instruments. However, a review of the literature from 2011 to 2022 indicated that relatively little research is available on the job satisfaction of private college lecturers in the Bornean states of Sabah and Sarawak. Research on job satisfaction was mainly conducted in Peninsular Malaysia that differs vastly from Sabah and Sarawak in terms of demographics, geography and other sociocultural variables. Most of the studies that examined educators' job satisfaction focused on secondary school teachers, while a few focused on public universities outside Sabah and Sarawak.

Therefore, more research examining lecturers' job satisfaction should be conducted using appropriate samples from the Bornean states to determine its robustness in other socio-environmental contexts. Further, since college student achievement is associated with lecturers' mental and emotional health as well as professional success, this study signalled an urgency to examine lecturers' job satisfaction as well as the types of support needed to enhance it.

This study is guided by two research objectives. First, since very little research has been conducted on the job satisfaction of private college lecturers from Sabah and Sarawak; this study aims to provide insight into the job satisfaction of lecturers

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from the two Bornean states. Second, findings would indicate if there is a need to enhance Malaysian college lecturers' job satisfaction. The findings of this study would inspire private colleges to identify the factors of job satisfaction and use them as a platform to enhance staff's affective attitudes toward their occupation. Specifically, the purpose of this study is to examine the job satisfaction of 60 private college lecturers in Malaysia in relation to age, gender and years of job experience. It is hypothesised that significant differences would be found in lecturers' job satisfaction in relation to age, gender and work experience at 0.05 level of significance. Further, this study focuses on nine factors of job satisfaction using the Job Satisfaction Survey (Spector, 1985), including pay, promotion, supervisor, benefits, rewards, the job itself, coworkers, operational procedures and communication.

Understanding the job satisfaction of private college lecturers not only leads to the identification of factors that cause high job satisfaction, but also enhances the recruitment and retention of high-calibre college lecturers. Findings of this study would be useful when referring to faculty motivation and performance issues, while efforts can be made to eliminate factors that cause dissatisfaction.

In light of the significance of the study, four research questions are formulated:

- Are there any significant differences in the lecturers' job satisfaction in relation to age?
- Are there any significant differences in the lecturers' job satisfaction in relation to gender?
- Are there any significant differences in lecturers' job satisfaction in relation to job experience?
- Are there any significant means (agreement/disagreement) in the nine factors of job satisfaction?

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Subjects

The sample consisted of 60 lecturers from five private colleges in Sabah and Sarawak, Malaysia. The colleges were randomly selected from 15 private colleges in both states using a table of random numbers. Drawn from communities that were culturally, linguistically and ethnically diverse, the sample was subsequently obtained with the cooperation of deans, principals and coordinators who agreed to share the survey link with their lecturers.

Roscoe (1975) proposed the following rule of thumb for determining sample size: sample sizes larger than 30 and less than 500 are appropriate for most research. Where samples are to be broken into sub-samples (e.g. male/females and juniors/seniors), a minimum sample size of 30 for each category is needed. In multivariate research (including multiple regression analyses), the sample size should be at least 10 times (or more) as large as the number of independent variables in the study. Since this study had three independent variables (age, gender and job experience), 60 subjects would be sufficient to yield reliable and valid results. Table 1 provides the demographic information of the sample.

TABLE 1: Demographic information of subjects

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age (years)	20-30	10	16.67%
	31-35	18	30.00%
	36-40	8	13.33%
	41-45	8	13.33%
	45-50	7	11.67%
	> 50	9	15.00%
	Total		60
Gender	Male	17	28.33%
	Female	43	71.67%
	Total	60	100.00%
Education	Bachelors	22	36.67%
	Masters	25	41.67%
	PhD	10	16.67%

	Diploma	3	5.00%
	Total	60	100.00%
Job (years)	1-5	14	23.33%
	6-10	14	23.33%
	11-15	11	18.33%
	16-20	6	10.00%
	> 20	15	25.00%
	Total	60	100.00%

B. Instrument

The job satisfaction of the participants was measured by the Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS) designed by Spector (1985). It consists of 36 items that assess employee attitudes toward nine factors of job satisfaction: (1) pay, (2) promotion, (3) supervisor, (4) benefits, (5) rewards and recognition, (6) job perceptions, (7) operating conditions, (8) coworkers and (9) communication. For this study, JSS was scored on a five-point Likert-type scale where 5=Strongly agree, 4=Agree, 3=Neutral, 2=Disagree and 1=Strongly Disagree. Responses were marked in a positive direction (high score=162-180, average score=126-161, low score=125 and below).

Tsounis and Sarafis (2018) translated the JSS into Greek and tested it with a sample of 239 employees of various specialties in drug addiction treatment. Confirmatory factor analysis for validity testing as well as internal consistency analysis for reliability were conducted. Results confirmed that the factor loads were high, ranging from 0.61 to 0.90; its reliability coefficients were satisfactory, with Cronbach’s alpha for eight of the dimensions ranging from 0.62 to 0.87. Cronbach’s alpha for the total scale was 0.87, while Gutman’s split-half coefficient was 0.88. Finally, Saane et al. (2003) who conducted a systematic review on several job satisfaction scales for use as evaluative tools in hospital environments, found that the JSS had reasonable test-retest reliabilities ranging from .64 to .80, besides having a construct validity of 0.78.

C. Data collection and analysis

The participants were required to complete the JSS online. Anonymity was strictly maintained to control bias; the only demographic information required was age, gender and job experience. Responses were computer-scored and data were then analysed using SPSS 26.0. A Mann-Whitney U test was used to determine if any significant gender differences existed in the job satisfaction of college lecturers, whereas a Kruskal-Wallis H test was used to determine if any significant age and experiential differences existed in the job satisfaction of the lecturers. A Wilcoxon signed-rank test was run to determine whether the lecturers had significantly high or low means in terms of agreement/disagreement in each of the nine factors of job satisfaction, using the test value of 4.0. The fixed variables were age, gender and job experience, while the dependent variable was the overall mean scores of lecturers’ job satisfaction.

IV. FINDINGS

The Kruskal-Wallis H test revealed significant age differences in the domain of coworkers and significant experiential differences in the domains of benefits and coworkers (see Table 2).

TABLE 2: p-value of parametric test results on job satisfaction in relation to age, gender and job experience

Factor	Age	Gender	Job experience
Pay	0.119	0.705	0.697
Promotion	0.402	0.386	0.600
Supervisor	0.388	0.741	0.345
Benefits	0.711	0.102	0.013**
Rewards	0.426	0.520	0.134
Job itself	0.073	0.200	0.221
Coworkers	0.031**	0.325	0.036**
Perceptions	0.468	0.416	0.897
Communcation	0.645	0.882	0.504

**significant at 0.05

Overall means showed that all the subgroups had low job satisfaction (see Table 3).

TABLE 3: Means of subgroups on overall job satisfaction

Gender	Frequency	Mean
Male	17	113.12
Female	43	115.74
Age	Frequency	Mean
25-30	10	120.80
31-35	18	117.50
36-40	8	120.13
41-45	8	100.12
46-50	7	108.57
> 50	9	118.78
Job experience (years)	Frequency	Mean
1-5	14	118.29
6-10	14	121.93
11-15	11	110.45
16-20	6	102.67
> 20	15	113.73

Results of the Wilcoxon signed-rank test on the nine factors of job satisfaction based on the test value of 4.0 showed that eight out of nine factors had significant means (see Table 4).

In terms of pay, the lecturers obtained a significantly low mean; a majority disagreed that (a) they were paid a fair amount for their work, (b) annual raises were regular at their college, (c) they felt appreciated by the college when they thought about their pay and (d) they felt satisfied with their chances for salary increases.

In terms of promotion, the lecturers obtained a significantly low mean; a majority disagreed that (a) there was a really chance for promotion on their job, (b) people who did well would have a fair chance of promotion, (c) people got ahead as fast in their college as they did in other places and (d) they were satisfied with their chances of promotion.

In terms of their direct supervisor (head/principal), the lecturers obtained a significantly low mean; a majority disagreed that (a) their direct supervisor was quite competent, (b) their direct supervisor was fair to them, (c) their direct supervisor showed great interest in subordinates' feelings and (d) they liked their direct supervisor.

In terms of benefits, the lecturers obtained a significantly low mean; a majority disagreed that (a) they were satisfied with their benefits, (b) benefits they received were as good as most other organisations, (c) their benefit package was equitable and (d) there were certain benefits that they should have, but did not.

In terms of recognition and rewards, lecturers obtained a significantly low mean; a majority disagreed that (a) they received recognition for doing a good job, (b) they felt that their work was appreciated, (c) they received the recognition they deserved for doing a good job and (d) they felt that their work was appreciated.

In terms of operating conditions, lecturers obtained a significantly high mean; a majority agreed that (a) many of the rules and procedures made doing a good job difficult, (b) their work was often hampered by red tape, (c) they had too much to do at work and (d) they had too much paperwork.

In terms of co-workers, the lecturers obtained a significantly low mean; a majority disagreed that (a) they liked the people they worked with, (b) they had competent colleagues; so, they did not have to work harder, (c) they enjoyed their co-workers and (d) there was not much bickering or backstabbing at work.

Finally, in terms of communication, the lecturers obtained a significantly low mean; a majority disagreed that (a) communication within their college was good, (b) they were clear about the goals of their college, (c) they knew what was going on with their college and (d) work assignments were fully explained.

TABLE 4: Wilcoxon signed-rank test on the nine factors of job satisfaction (test value = 4.0)

Factor	Median	Test statistic	<i>Sig. (2-tailed)</i>	
Pay	3.00	6.743	< 0.001*	Sig. disagree
Promotion	3.25	6.747	< 0.001*	Sig. disagree
Supervisor	3.50	6.636	< 0.001*	Sig. disagree
Benefits	3.25	6.747	< 0.001*	Sig. disagree
Rewards	3.13	6.690	< 0.001*	Sig. disagree
Job itself	2.00	6.638	< 0.014**	Sig. disagree
Coworkers	3.25	6.751	< 0.001*	Sig. disagree
Perceptions	4.00	6.756	0.157	Not sig.
Communcation	3.50	6.693	< 0.001*	Sig. disagree

* significant at 0.001; ** significant at 0.05

V. DISCUSSION, IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Discussion

Results of this study indicated that some college lecturers in Sabah and Sarawak had low job satisfaction. Findings were supported by previous studies done in Malaysia. Huda et al. (2004) found that job dissatisfaction was prevalent among lecturers. Factors that were significantly related to job dissatisfaction were decision authority, decision latitude, psychological stressors, job strain, psychological job demand and depression. Additionally, Wong and Heng (2009), who examined the job satisfaction of faculty members at two Malaysian universities, found that relevant sources of faculty dissatisfaction were reflected by the absence of motivators, including personal achievement, personal growth, interpersonal relations, recognition, responsibility, supervision, the work itself, and the overall working conditions.

Further, Henny et al. (2014) found that burnout tended to be prevalent among academicians with job satisfaction as the strongest predictor. Junior academicians on contract employment, clinical academicians and those with lower salary tended to exhibit job dissatisfaction. The chances of experiencing burnout among academicians who were dissatisfied with their job were seven times higher compared to those who were satisfied with their job. Finally, Mohamed et al. (2021) who examined burnout, psychological distress and job satisfaction among academic and non-academic staff at a public university in Malaysia, found that academicians demonstrated greater burnout levels and psychological distress than non-academicians. Academicians tended to experience high levels of burnout in relation to personal, work and client-related matters, which in turn, significantly reduced their job satisfaction.

B. Implications and recommendations

In light of the findings, several implications were made with regards to the job satisfaction among private college lecturers. Wong and Heng (2009) who found that motivator or intrinsic factors were strongly related to job dissatisfaction, suggested that concerted efforts be made to improve faculty job satisfaction based on these factors. Private college lecturers' teaching and research should be enriched to encourage them to attain self-actualisation, and subsequently, job satisfaction. Improving motivator or intrinsic factors will allow them to have greater flexibility and adaptability to changing conditions, while favourable interpersonal relationships will facilitate effective teaching.

First, university management styles tended to have a significant impact on faculty job satisfaction (Amazta & Idrisa, 2011). To enhance job satisfaction of private college lecturers, management can practise behavioural decision-making styles that are contiguous and situational, whereby leaders are task- and people-oriented. While avoiding a dominant decision-making style, management can also establish good rapport with faculty to gain deeper insight into their problems and concerns. In brief, it is suggested that management be authoritative and communicative, being neither too strict nor too lenient when dealing with difficult situations.

Second, bureaucratic, innovative and supportive organisational cultures tend to have significant relationships with faculty job satisfaction (Chan, Wong & Wok, 2017). The bureaucratic culture, practised in most Malaysian organisations, emphasises strict formality, with a clear line of authority and responsibilities that encourages faculty to work independently. Institutionalised rules and regulations ensure that faculty perform their duties and responsibilities to their fullest potential. To enhance job satisfaction of college lecturers, management can demonstrate fairness in terms of human resource practices to augment adherence to organisational rules and regulations. Additionally, colleges can implement various research and innovation programs to foster lecturers' cognitive and critical thinking skills, besides encouraging them to join such extracurricular activities as open days, education carnivals, team-building retreats and community relations that promote staff identification in a supportive environment.

Third, faculty job satisfaction tends to significantly mediate the relationship between strategic performance measurement system (SPMS) and work performance (Janudin & Halim, 2018). SPMS is designed to present financial and non-financial measures, covering different perspectives that can translate strategies into coherent performance measures. Colleges can adopt SPMS that provides the impetus to nurture and improve faculty capabilities to the fullest potential. Additionally, to help strengthen the long-term plan of the current Malaysian Education Blueprint, colleges should see that their SPMS function comprehensively to transform higher education delivery.

Fourth, internal corporate social responsibility practices (employee empowerment, employment stability and employee engagement) tend to promote faculty job satisfaction (Hossen, Chan & Hasan, 2020). Since employees and employers tend to be keen in establishing interactive relationships in the form of exchange and mutual benefits, management can see that lecturers experience high employment stability and empowerment. Management can also strive to have regular personal interactions with lecturers since a reciprocal connection will increase their enthusiasm and loyalty.

Fifth, transformational leadership components (ideal influence, intellectual stimulation, individual considerations and inspirational motivation) tend to play an important role in nurturing and developing positive attitudes among faculty to achieve specific goals (Mahzan & Nordin, 2021). Management that practises transformational leadership can act as catalysts that are motivated, goal-oriented and far-sighted with the faculty. Hence, colleges can adopt transformational leadership to cultivate the spirit of cooperation among faculty in decision making, which in turn, increases their organisational commitment.

Sixth, stress of academic staff tends to be primarily related to workload, which in turn affects their job satisfaction and performance (Janib et al., 2021). Workload-stress concentration among Malaysian faculties, especially those in research-based universities, together with a heavy workload, often adversely affects faculty performance, job satisfaction and career commitment. Since job satisfaction is interrelated with workload and faculty performance, college policies can include monitoring and regulating academic staff's stress levels if they aim to improve their national and international performance rankings. Further, the relationship between commitment and job satisfaction also tends to be significantly mediated by self-efficacy (Mokhtar et al., 2023); hence, steps can be taken to enhance teacher self-efficacy to promote higher commitment, job satisfaction and task performance.

Lastly, college teachers' overall career satisfaction and job fulfillment tend to be significantly linked to professional identity and career calling (Wu et al, 2024). Teacher preparation programs can capitalize on the professional identity, career satisfaction and career calling of preservice teachers to better prepare them for a rewarding and gratifying career. To reinforce their professional identity, career satisfaction and career calling, support structures to foster a sense of autonomy, competence, and purpose can be provided. Lastly, providing chances for professional development to preservice teachers will enhance their sense of job satisfaction and motivation to excel in their positions. On the other hand, current teachers need to have a better understanding of the variables affecting career satisfaction. To lessen burnout and improve overall wellbeing among teachers, supportive work environments that emphasize professional identity, career calling and psychological empowerment can be created.

To conclude, this research topic can be explored with a larger, more heterogeneous sample to increase generalisability of instrumentation as well as findings. Since the JSS has not been extensively used in the Malaysian context before, its reliability and validity should be re-examined using multicultural samples from different states.

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